

Evidence Based Data Extraction and RTD Classification of Primary Studies

Paper	DTR	Description	What phenomenon is discussed in the article? How does the article address this phenomenon? Why does this correspond to the type of DTR?	
S1	Type 2: Incompatible Implementation	<p>It describes requirements change management. The proposed tool analyzes technical, functional, and business impacts to ensure that software updates (the implementation) accurately reflect dynamic conditions. This directly addresses the cause of Type 2 Debt, which is the discrepancy between what was specified and what is actually encoded.</p>	<p>The central phenomenon addressed in the article is Requirements Change Management and, more specifically, change impact analysis.</p> <p>The article proposes the use of Large Language Models (LLMs), specifically GPT-4. The system segments the existing requirements documentation and converts it into vector representations (embeddings). When a new change request is submitted, it is also converted into embeddings, and the system performs a semantic search to identify the parts of the documentation that will be most affected. GPT-4 then utilizes this information to conduct a multi-dimensional impact analysis: technical, functional, business, and stakeholder impact.</p> <p>The tool aims to prevent the mismatch between stakeholders' objectives and the actual implementation of the system, corresponding to the mitigation of Type 2 Requirements Technical Debt (RTD).</p>	Tool

S2	Type 1: Requirement Smells	<p>It focuses on the detection of defects within requirements written in Natural Language. The objective of the study is to evaluate the capability of tools (in this case, ChatGPT) to identify quality issues in existing documentation.</p>	<p>The article addresses inconsistency in software requirements written in natural language. The study defines inconsistency as a situation in which two or more requirements disagree with each other and contain conflicting or contradictory descriptions regarding the expected behavior of the specified system.</p> <p>A practical experiment was conducted to measure the ability of ChatGPT (GPT-3.5) to automatically identify these inconsistency defects. Four original requirements documents were selected (Coffee machine, E-shop, Library, and ETCS). The original documents were perturbed by injecting mutant requirements new requirements generated by ChatGPT itself specifically designed to conflict with the existing ones.</p> <p>Subsequently, ChatGPT was prompted to analyze the mutated document to identify the pairs of conflicting requirements. Finally, the artificial intelligence's performance was compared with the human judgment of experts (students with experience in Requirements Engineering), evaluating metrics such as precision and recall to determine if the tool can complement manual analysis.</p> <p>The objective of the article is to accelerate the textual refinement process to obtain a high-quality requirements document that is free of logical conflicts. Therefore, it deals strictly with documentation defects and its formalized language. The debt addressed in the study is generated and analyzed during the requirements formalization phase in the specification document, using natural language. This aligns with the mitigation of Type 1 RTD.</p>	Approach
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S3	Type 1: Requirement Smells	<p>The article focuses specifically on anaphoric ambiguity in requirements, which occurs when a pronoun can refer to different entities in the text, leading to multiple interpretations. It seeks to detect these occurrences of ambiguous pronouns.</p>	<p>The article addresses anaphoric ambiguity in requirements specified in natural language. In Requirements Engineering, this phenomenon occurs when a pronoun, known as an anaphora, can refer to multiple different entities previously mentioned in the text (referred to as antecedents).</p> <p>The article addresses the problem by developing and empirically comparing an automated multi-solution approach based on state-of-the-art Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Machine Learning technologies. The processing of the phenomenon is divided into two complementary tasks:</p> <p>Ambiguity Detection: The primary focus in Requirements Engineering is to identify pronoun occurrences that are genuinely ambiguous to alert human analysts.</p> <p>Anaphora Resolution (Interpretation): Discovering and suggesting the most likely and correct antecedent for the analyzed pronoun.</p> <p>Pronoun-generated ambiguity is a writing defect introduced during the requirements formalization phase in the Software Requirements Specification (SRS) document using natural language. This corresponds to Type 1 RTD.</p>	Approac h
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S4	Type 1: Requirement Smells	<p>It investigates the effectiveness of GPT-4 in detecting three main categories of defects in SRS (Software Requirements Specification) documents: ambiguity, inconsistency, and incompleteness. A significant portion of its analysis is dedicated to detecting issues in the formalization of requirements, both in natural language and in graphical models.</p>	<p>The central phenomenon addressed in the article is the presence of defects in Software Requirements Specification (SRS) documents, specifically focusing on three main issues: ambiguities, inconsistencies, and incompleteness. The study analyzes how these defects manifest during the formalization of requirements, both in natural language writing and in visual representation through graphical models (UML diagrams).</p> <p>The article investigates the effectiveness of using Large Language Models (LLMs), specifically GPT-4 and GPT-4 Vision, to automate the detection of these defects. The authors' approach includes:</p> <p>Industrial Case Study: Utilizing a real, complex, and extensive Software Requirements Specification (SRS) document (52 pages) for a Mechanical Lung Ventilator (MLV), which contains both text and UML diagrams.</p> <p>Extraction and Analysis (Zero-shot): The researchers extract the text and image descriptions (using GPT-4 Vision) and provide prompts to GPT-4 to evaluate specific sections of the document for unclear sentences, contradictions, or missing information.</p> <p>Qualitative and Quantitative Evaluation: The article not only verifies whether the AI can find the errors but also measures the precision of these detections (how many alarms were true positives) and classifies the severity of the identified defects on a scale of 1 to 5, comparing the AI's results with the defects found by human experts during the formal modeling of the system.</p> <p>The article actively searches for structural problems in both language and diagrams, guiding the AI to identify ambiguities and inconsistencies, which aligns with the mitigation of Type 1 RTD.</p>	LLM
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S5	<p>Type 1: Requirement Smells and Type 0: Incomplete Stakeholder Needs.</p>	<p>It focuses on improving the writing quality of requirements, addressing problematic constructions in natural language. Additionally, it proposes mechanisms to detect and fill gaps in security requirements specifications, which is directly related to Incomplete Stakeholder Needs (Type 0 RTD).</p>	<p>The article addresses the introduction of critical software vulnerabilities caused by security requirements that are incorrect, vague (ambiguous), or missing (incomplete) during the elicitation and design phases of the Software Development Lifecycle.</p> <p>To combat these issues, the article proposes an automated mechanism divided into two main components integrated as web services:</p> <p>SSRS Component (Software Security Requirements Specification): Addresses the lack of formalization by extracting requirements from natural language and converting them into formal representations. It utilizes Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques to perform syntactic and semantic analyses, identifying the core concepts of a requirement (such as Actors, Actions, Objects, and Priority) and mapping them into ontology instances.</p> <p>SSRVV Component (Software Security Requirements Verification & Validation): Evaluates the correctness and completeness of the requirements formalized by the SSRS. It compares the user-defined requirements against a curated knowledge base (a list of security requirements well-defined by experts) using word similarity checks. Based on this, the system generates reports highlighting inconsistencies and offering refinement recommendations.</p> <p>The tool goes beyond simple grammatical correction and verifies the completeness of what has been specified. It achieves this through "Complementary Recommendations": when analyzing a security objective, the system identifies gaps and suggests related additional requirements that the user omitted, corresponding to Type 0 RTD. Furthermore, it addresses "vague" and "incorrect" requirements. The SSRVV component acts as a refactorer for these "requirements smells" by</p>	Tool
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			suggesting alternative and less ambiguous priority terms, corresponding to Type 1 RTD.	
S6	Type 0: Incomplete Stakeholder Needs	The study investigates the integration of Artificial Intelligence, specifically the GPT-3.5 and GPT-4 models, into the teaching of requirements traceability within software engineering. The authors conducted an experiment comparing the ability of Master's students and LLMs to link technical specifications to their source artifacts, such as interview transcripts and prototypes.	<p>The article addresses the phenomenon of requirements traceability, which is the process of linking each requirement specification to its source artifact (such as interview transcripts, prototypes, or project descriptions) where the client originally requested that need.</p> <p>The article proposes an approach that incorporates LLMs, specifically GPT-3.5 and GPT-4, as supporting tools for traceability engineering and education. In practice, the study conducted an experiment where both software engineering students and AI models were provided with interview transcripts, visual artifacts, and a final list of Software SRS to perform the traceability mapping.</p> <p>The approach corresponds to the prevention of Type 0 RTD because the central focus of the technique is to ensure that no client needs have been omitted or neglected during the analysis.</p>	LLM

S7	<p>Type 0: Incomplete Stakeholder Needs. And Type 1: Requirement Smells</p>	<p>The article investigates whether ChatGPT can assist in eliciting a complete set of needs for Trustworthy AI systems. Furthermore, it dedicates part of its methodology to evaluating the quality of written requirements, utilizing attributes aimed at detecting smells (or issues in text formalization).</p>	<p>The article addresses the use of Large Language Models (LLMs), specifically ChatGPT, to assist in the Requirements Elicitation process.</p> <p>The article conducts an empirical study in which researchers developed six prompts to extract Trustworthy AI requirements. However, they deliberately omitted critical topics (such as Security, Regulation, and Accountability) from the questions to test whether ChatGPT and humans would spontaneously identify and suggest these requirements in the final open-ended question. They collected six ChatGPT-generated responses and 30 responses formulated by five human experts in requirements engineering. Finally, a different group of five experts conducted a "blind" evaluation (without knowing whether the author was human or AI) to assess the quality of the 36 sets of requirements.</p> <p>The study simulated the risk of incurring Type 0 Debt by testing ChatGPT's level of domain awareness. Since the researchers deliberately omitted crucial factors, they observed that ChatGPT failed to generate requirements related to Accountability, Regulations, and Safety in its unsolicited response. This corresponds perfectly to Type 0 RTD. The study also measured, through the Unambiguity attribute, whether the presentation of the requirements was unclear, imprecise, and subject to multiple interpretations.</p>	LLM
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S8	Type 1: Requirement Smells	<p>The article proposes the use of a controlled natural language (Rimay) to rewrite these requirements in a disciplined manner, tackling the problem precisely during the formalization and writing phase. It mentions that the proposed tool (PASKA) aims to improve quality attributes such as "clarity," "atomicity," and "correctness." This mirrors your definition of Type 1 RTD, which refers to the violation of requirements quality standards (such as ISO/IEC 29148).</p>	<p>The article focuses on the phenomenon of quality issues in the writing of natural language (NL) requirements specifications, which are referred to in the literature as Requirement Smells.</p> <p>The tool utilizes advanced NLP techniques, such as tokenization, POS tagging, glossary lookup, and parsing, combined with tree-pattern matching (Tregex) and structural rules to automatically locate nine types of smells within functional requirements documents.</p> <p>The tool provides actionable recommendations for correction by cross-referencing the flawed requirement with the patterns of a Controlled Natural Language (CNL) called Rimay. The tool suggests an appropriate Rimay pattern to guide analysts in rewriting the requirement, converting vague text into a structured, precise, and unambiguous format, aligning with the mitigation of Type 1 RTD.</p>	Tool
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S9	Type 1: Requirement Smells	<p>The article proposes the use of Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Machine Learning to address requirements ambiguity and the subjectivity inherent in manual methods. It explicitly mentions the goal of "combating issues related to requirements ambiguity" and utilizes text preprocessing techniques (tokenization, redundancy removal) to "clean" and structure the requirements content.</p>	<p>The article addresses the phenomenon of ambiguity and subjectivity inherent in the documentation and prioritization of software requirements in Agile Development environments.</p> <p>To solve this problem, the article proposes an innovative model called RAR-P (Rule-Based Automated Requirements Prioritization), which replaces subjective human evaluation with an algorithmic and data-driven approach. The study treats the phenomenon as follows:</p> <p>The model extracts and processes the natural language of the requirements to understand it computationally and resolve ambiguity issues. The requirements undergo a cleaning stage that involves converting to lowercase, removing punctuation and stopwords, tokenization, and eliminating redundancies to standardize the data. Next, the TF-IDF (Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency) technique is used to transform the texts into numerical vectors, identifying the actual importance of specific terms. The "cosine similarity" metric is then used to group requirements that are semantically close, without relying on biased human interpretations. Finally, using the K-Means Machine Learning algorithm, the model organizes large volumes of text into logical clusters, allowing for systematic and impartial prioritization.</p> <p>The approach uses NLP to automate meaning extraction and clean the texts of ambiguities and redundancies, eliminating the "smells" left by imperfect human writing, aligning with Type 1 RTD.</p>	Approach
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S10	Type 1: Requirement Smells	The article proposes the detection of 17 smells, offering NLP methods to detect anomalies in requirements specification (such as ambiguity and grammatical malformation).	<p>The article addresses the phenomenon of linguistic bad smells in goal-oriented requirements models, specifically in the Goal-oriented Requirement Language (GRL) and its textual representation (TGRL). These bad smells represent poor practices or linguistic anomalies, such as unclear or ambiguous goal statements, and conflicting or contradictory requirements.</p> <p>The article treats this phenomenon by proposing a Natural Language Processing (NLP) based approach to detect and mitigate these anomalies. The study handles the problem through:</p> <p>Identification and Classification: The study catalogs 17 linguistic bad smells that affect the quality of goal models and classifies them into four categories: Syntax, Semantics, Pragmatics, and Complexity.</p> <p>Automated Tool Development: The authors develop detection methods using NLP techniques (such as semantic similarity analysis, POS tagging, natural language inference, etc.) and implement an automated tool capable of identifying 12 of these 17 bad smells directly in TGRL textual model files.</p> <p>The approach identifies and corrects linguistic anomalies in textual/graphical models before system development, acting directly on the mitigation of Type 1 RTD.</p>	Approac h
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S11	Type 1: Requirement Smells	<p>It focuses on the challenges posed by the use of natural language in requirements specification. It proposes a framework to mitigate ambiguities by transforming unstructured text into formal conceptual models. By using ChatGPT to extract and structure these elements into a rigid format (e.g., quadruples for expected effects or triples for expectation relationships), the article seeks to formalize the interpretation of requirements, thereby reducing the Technical Debt (TD) generated by the subjective interpretation of vague texts.</p>	<p>The article addresses the inherent imprecision of natural language used in writing requirements documents. The authors highlight that requirements provided by users and clients are typically expressed in natural language and that the use of this imprecise language frequently leads to vagueness, incompleteness, and ambiguity.</p> <p>To solve this problem, an automated framework for generating requirements models is proposed. The framework employs ChatGPT using the zero-shot learning technique to read natural language requirements texts. Through domain-specific prompts focused on embedded systems, structured elements are extracted from the ambiguous text and classified into rigid categories (such as Software, System Device, External Entity, System Capability, Expected Effect, and Expectation Relationship).</p> <p>The extracted elements are then composed using predefined rules to generate a formal conceptual model, specifically a Problem Diagram based on the Problem Frame approach.</p> <p>By mapping free text into rigorous tuples and formal diagrams, the framework eliminates the subjectivity of natural language and textual requirements potentially filled with smells, aligning with the resolution of Type 1 RTD.</p>	LLM
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S12	Type 2: Incompatible Implementation	<p>The central problem identified by the authors is that LLM-based code generation tools frequently fail to create systems that adhere to specified requirements. The article states that, in standard approaches, the model-generated implementation violates all specified requirements and exhibits a lack of alignment that makes it difficult to ensure the code's behavior reflects the original intent.</p>	<p>The article addresses the difficulty and failure of LLMs in generating complete and correct software systems directly from requirements. The authors identify that, in traditional LLM-based code generation approaches, there is a severe lack of alignment between the generated code and the specification, resulting in implementations that violate the desired requirements and introduce errors that are difficult for developers to identify.</p> <p>The approach allows each requirement to be translated directly into a dedicated and separate code module (known as a b-thread). This eliminates the need for the LLM to have a global and complex view of the system, allowing it to focus on implementing what should and should not happen for one specific requirement at a time. An execution engine interprets and weaves these separate modules together to generate a cohesive system behavior that respects the original specifications.</p> <p>By isolating the code for each requirement, the approach facilitates the use of formal verification techniques (such as model-checking) to automatically identify, validate, and correct errors and hallucinations introduced by the LLMs.</p> <p>By ensuring that the LLM generated implementation is aligned, correct, and formally verified against the specification, the article focuses strictly on guaranteeing that the code fulfills the promise of the original requirements, thus combating Type 2 RTD.</p>	Approach
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S13	Type 1: Requirement Smells	<p>The article focuses on the requirements formalization phase, transforming textual descriptions (natural language) into formal models (in this case, UML-based Alf models and CSP models). By proposing a metamodel and an automated validation tool to detect inconsistencies, naming rule violations, and logical errors in requirements models (UML/Alf), the article directly addresses the quality of the technical specification.</p>	<p>The article addresses the semantic gaps and inconsistencies that arise when stakeholder requirements (typically described textually in natural language) are abstracted and transformed into modeling languages during the requirements analysis and design phases.</p> <p>To solve this problem, an executable framework focused on modeling and validation is proposed, utilizing the following strategies:</p> <p>Formal Modeling: It uses the Alf language (a textual notation for UML) to create initial requirements models and transforms them into CSP (Communicating Sequential Processes) models to allow for logical and behavioral simulations.</p> <p>Consistency Validation (EVL): It employs the Epsilon Validation Language (EVL) to automatically validate the generated models against meta-rules, business constraints, and logic.</p> <p>Formalization Check: Finally, the system checks for formalization flaws, such as naming convention errors or semantic and logical ambiguities.</p> <p>In addition to generating a validation report with captured errors and warnings, the framework utilizes a mechanism to automatically repair the inconsistencies and semantic gaps found in the models.</p> <p>When the article defines rigorous rules to check variable names, inheritance consistency, and logical constraints, it is identifying and correcting problematic constructs that violate specification quality standards, aligning with the resolution of Type 1 RTD.</p>	Approach
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S14	Type 0: Incomplete Stakeholder Needs	<p>The article states that, in RE, it is not always assumed that the initial description of requirements is complete, which can lead to missing requirements or changes. The proposed approach aims to "address requirement gaps." The final objective of the method is to complete missing requirements by connecting to an external knowledge base to expand the set of keywords.</p>	<p>The article addresses the fact that the initial requirements description in software projects is rarely complete, frequently leading to missing requirements, gaps, or changes. Furthermore, the difficulty in achieving full requirements acquisition is driven by semantic understanding challenges faced by users and requirements engineers who possess different levels of domain knowledge.</p> <p>To solve this, the article proposes an unsupervised keyword extraction method based on Natural Language Processing (NLP), specifically utilizing the BERT model. It identifies and extracts keywords and key phrases already explicit in the initial requirements text. It then connects these extracted words to external knowledge bases to retrieve context, synonyms, and associated domain concepts. Based on this context, the model predicts new keywords and concepts that were not in the original text but are semantically essential to the domain. This expanded information is then suggested to users via a dropdown list in a modeling tool, allowing them to fill the gaps semi-automatically during system design.</p> <p>The objective of the article is to mitigate the omission of information and complete missing requirements, aligning with the mitigation of Type 0 RTD.</p>	Approach
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S15	Type 0: Incomplete Stakeholder Needs	<p>The article addresses the fact that eliciting requirements from many stakeholders is difficult and that manually reading/managing a large volume of responses is time-consuming. By automating this process using NLP, the method aims to ensure that stakeholder responses are processed to find an agreed-upon requirement that represents the majority. This helps avoid accidental neglect caused by the inability to manually process large volumes of data.</p>	<p>The article addresses the challenge of eliciting and collecting requirements from a large number of distributed stakeholders, each with their own concerns and needs. It also tackles the difficulty and excessive time required to manually read, manage, and extract an "agreed requirement" from a high volume of natural language responses provided by stakeholders in open-ended questionnaires.</p> <p>An automated approach is proposed, utilizing NLP techniques to analyze the responses from all stakeholders and identify which one best represents the majority opinion. The method operates as follows: the textual responses undergo tokenization, stop word removal, and lemmatization to extract a list of the most relevant terms. The responses are represented using the Vector Space Model (VSM), and then mathematical similarity metrics (such as Cosine, Jaccard, Overlap, and Dice) are used to create a similarity matrix that compares each response against all others. The approach calculates a score for each response based on these comparisons and automatically selects the response with the highest score, which serves as the representative initial requirement (the agreed requirement).</p> <p>The article resolves the risk of accidental neglect of user needs in large-scale systems, aligning with Type 0 RTD.</p>	Approach
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S16	Type 0: Incomplete Stakeholder Needs	<p>The article seeks to provide a strategy to guide stakeholders (both computer science professionals and laypeople) through the elicitation process, helping to identify comprehensive and consistent requirements. It proposes a tool ("SRE tool") focused on the requirements elicitation phase and the identification of stakeholder needs.</p>	<p>The main phenomenon addressed in the article is Requirements Elicitation and the difficulty in extracting, understanding, and documenting stakeholder needs and desires in a complete and correct manner. The text highlights that end-users and domain experts often do not have a background in software development and lack fundamental skills for requirements elicitation.</p> <p>To mitigate elicitation difficulties, the authors propose the development of a Software Requirements Elicitation (SRE) tool based on pattern reusability. This tool seeks to guide stakeholders whether they are from the computing field or laypeople by offering reusable templates that help identify and organize functional requirements, non-functional requirements, and business rules according to specific domains.</p> <p>This aligns with Type 0 RTD because the central objective of the approach is to prevent stakeholder needs from being neglected, forgotten, or left incomplete.</p>	Tool
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S17	Type 2: Incompatible Implementation	<p>The article defines software verification as the process of ensuring that a system meets specific requirements. The activities conducted in the study consist of providing GPT-3.5 with a code snippet and a series of requirements, asking whether or not the code fulfills what was specified.</p>	<p>The article addresses source code verification, which is the process performed during the software development life cycle (SDLC) to ensure and evaluate whether a system or product meets specific requirements.</p> <p>GPT-3.5 is used as a tool to automate and assist in the analysis of requirements specifications. The methodology consists of providing the AI model with a source code snippet along with a series of requirements written in natural language. Subsequently, the authors ask GPT-3.5 if the provided code satisfies the required specifications and evaluate the justifications given by the model. The study conducts this through scenarios with increasing levels of complexity in both code and requirements, culminating in tests where the code purposefully fails to meet the specifications to test the model's detection capabilities.</p> <p>The practical objective of the experiment is to find discrepancies between the requirements specification and the code implemented by the developer, aligning with Type 2 RTD.</p>	LLM
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S18	Type 0: Incomplete Stakeholder Needs. And Type 1: Requirement Smells	<p>The tool utilizes situational parameters related to stakeholders (such as expressiveness, availability, and location) to recommend the correct technique. This aims to mitigate the risk of neglecting the needs of specific groups or failing to gather a complete set of requirements. Although the tool detailed in the text focuses on elicitation, the broader proposed framework, called SRAAF (Software Requirement Ambiguity Avoidance Framework), was specifically designed to avoid ambiguity, which is the core characteristic of requirement smells.</p>	<p>The article addresses the ambiguity problems inherent in requirements documents written in natural language and the difficulty in extracting complete requirements due to the poor selection of elicitation techniques.</p> <p>The tool assists requirements engineers in selecting the most appropriate technique by using a mapping of situational parameters divided into three categories: project, requirements engineer, and stakeholders. The second phase of the SRAAF framework consists of applying NLP techniques to the requirements before they are finalized in the Software Requirements Specification (SRS) document. NLP is applied to verify and correct various types of ambiguity in the elicited requirements.</p> <p>The article focuses on elicitation, which is the process of identifying stakeholder needs, corresponding to Type 0 RTD. The article also covers the use of NLP techniques to check and eliminate ambiguity before the requirements are formalized and finalized in the SRS, corresponding to Type 1 RTD.</p>	Tool
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S19	Type 1: Requirement Smells	<p>The article proposes the BERDD (Behaviour Engineering-Based Requirement Defects Detection) approach to detect defects during the requirements analysis and change management phases. The primary objective is to identify specific defects in the requirements documentation: ambiguity, inconsistency, redundancy, and incompleteness.</p>	<p>The article addresses the occurrence and persistence of software requirements defects, specifically during the requirements analysis and requirements change management phases. The study focuses on the detection of the four most common types of defects found in requirements specifications: incompleteness, inconsistency, redundancy, and ambiguity.</p> <p>The article proposes a structured and automated approach called BERDD. The method first translates the original software requirements into graphical models called Behavior Trees (BTs). It establishes a normal form for requirements based on the "Axiom of Inertia," requiring that every well-formed requirement possesses a logical precondition, a trigger event, and a post-condition. The graphical models (BTs) are then automatically translated, via XML files, into a formal ontology language called OWL (Web Ontology Language). Finally, a tool called RDI (Requirements Defects Identifier) executes semantic queries (using the SPARQL language) on the OWL knowledge base to find rule violations, automatically detecting defects (ambiguities, inconsistencies, etc.).</p> <p>The BERDD approach focuses on the transition from natural language requirements to graphical models and formal representations, searching for defects inherent in the way these requirements were expressed and connected, aligning with Type 1 RTD.</p>	Approach
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S20	Type 0: Incomplete Stakeholder Needs	<p>The article proposes a method to accurately identify user requirements from massive user data. The central objective of the study is to fill gaps in the understanding of what users truly desire and how those desires evolve, avoiding the neglect of needs from this critical stakeholder group.</p>	<p>The article addresses the challenge of accurately and efficiently extracting what users truly need from a massive amount of data, given the constraints of time and cost.</p> <p>The problem is addressed by proposing a method (research framework) for the dynamic analysis and forecasting of user requirements using NLP. The approach handles dynamic evolution through three main stages:</p> <p>Topic Extraction: It utilizes tools to collect thousands of online user reviews and applies the LDA (Latent Dirichlet Allocation) probabilistic model to automatically discover latent requirement topics within the texts.</p> <p>Evolution Analysis (IPA-Kano): It employs sentiment analysis dictionaries (SnowNLP) to process the text and calculate the importance and satisfaction linked to each requirement across different time windows.</p> <p>Forecasting (LSTM Model): It uses an LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory) recurrent neural network to analyze time series and predict future trends in the importance and satisfaction of these requirements, helping to identify and prioritize key demands for product design.</p> <p>The objective of the article is to avoid the omission of the actual needs of end-users (a stakeholder group) over time, aligning with Type 0 RTD.</p>	Approac h
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S21	Type 1: Requirement Smells	The primary objective of the proposed tool (ReqGo) is to address requirements ambiguity. The tool utilizes NLP to automatically identify ambiguous terms and vague requirements.	<p>The article addresses the phenomenon of ambiguity in software requirements written in natural language, as well as the inefficiency and error-proneness associated with the manual process of labeling and classifying these requirements.</p> <p>The study tackles this phenomenon by proposing and evaluating a semi-automated requirements management tool called ReqGo. The tool addresses ambiguity and manual classification as follows: it utilizes NLP techniques and Google's Universal Sentence Encoder method (along with TensorFlow.js) to transform text into vectors and analyze the semantic similarity of words. The system defines a threshold value; if a requirement's semantics exceed this value, it is flagged as ambiguous. When ambiguous or vague terms are detected, the tool notifies the user (via warning messages in the interface), allowing preventive actions to be taken by requirements engineers before development proceeds. To avoid errors in the manual labeling process, ReqGo implements the Naive Bayes machine learning algorithm. Before classification, the natural language requirement text is normalized (through Tokenization, Part-Of-Speech tagging, and Lemmatization). Subsequently, the algorithm performs a binary classification of the requirements into Functional and Non-Functional with high precision.</p> <p>The article emphasizes that the primary objective is to identify ambiguous terms, classify requirements correctly, and discover requirements defects at an early stage, corresponding to Type 1 RTD.</p>	Tool
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S22	<p>Type 1: Requirement Smells and Type 2: Incompatible Implementation</p>	<p>The article addresses a "Triplet Structure" (Subject, Predicate, Object) as a technique for writing high-quality requirements, aiming to reduce ambiguities and inconsistencies.</p> <p>Although the primary focus is on the writing phase (Type 1 RTD), the ultimate goal of the proposed technique is to prevent the implemented software from deviating from the specification, which aligns with the definition of Type 2 Debt.</p>	<p>The article addresses the presence of ambiguity, inconsistency, incompleteness, and a lack of clarity in software requirements specifications when they are written in natural language.</p> <p>The article proposes a solution by introducing a model that restricts and standardizes requirements writing into a simple syntactic structure of Subject, Predicate, and Object (SPO). The objective is to eliminate superfluous details and force the specification to be "simple, concise, and clear," where the subject is the actor, the predicate is the operation, and the object is the software component. To operationalize this structure, the article describes the development of a tool supported by Natural Language Processing (NLP) (inspired by the Stanford NLP Group parser). This tool automatically detects ambiguous, incomplete, or imprecise sentences and even identifies missing words in the text. After detection, the tool converts functional requirements from a free-text format into the triplet structure.</p> <p>The article functions as a smell detector, analyzing the syntactic and semantic structure of sentences to locate imprecise and defective constructs, aligning with Type 1 Requirements Technical Debt (RTD). By structuring the requirements so that they already explicitly contain the methods and classes to be coded, the approach ensures requirements traceability and reduces the risk of the development team programming an inadequate solution or one that differs from the original stakeholder objective, thus tackling RTD Type 2.</p>	Tool
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S23	Type 2: Incompatible Implementation	<p>The article highlights that impact analysis is necessary not only for other requirements but also to evaluate the effect of changes on traceable lower-level objects, such as software design and source code. The objective of the proposed prediction model is to automate this analysis to ensure that, when a requirement changes, all dependencies are identified, thereby preventing incompatibility between what was specified (SRS) and the final product.</p>	<p>The article addresses the continuous change of software requirements and the challenge of performing Change Impact Analysis (CIA). During development, when a single requirement statement is altered in the Software Requirements Specification (SRS), it can trigger multiple cascading modifications throughout the system. The article highlights that manual analysis of how these changes affect other requirements and artifacts is time-consuming, labor-intensive, error-prone, and can lead to significant inconsistencies in the specification.</p> <p>To resolve the difficulties and errors of manual analysis, the article proposes the development of an automated prediction model that combines Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Machine Learning (ML) techniques. Textual documents (requirements specifications and change requests) are processed using techniques such as tokenization, lemmatization, Bag of Words (TF-IDF), and Word Embeddings (including BERT) to capture semantic, syntactic, and contextual similarities between the texts.</p> <p>Algorithms such as Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest, and Naive Bayes are trained on this data to identify relationships and dependencies. Consequently, the model predicts a ranked list indicating which requirements are most likely to be impacted by a new change request. The model also includes human-in-the-loop participation, where an analyst evaluates the system's predictions (approving or disapproving suggested impacts), helping the algorithm tune its precision and continuously improve.</p> <p>The article states that impact analysis is necessary to evaluate the effect of</p>	Approach
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			<p>requirements changes on traceable lower-level objects, such as software design and source code. When analysis is performed manually and errors occur, the changes requested by stakeholders (which update the SRS) fail to be reflected at the source code level. Therefore, by automating and providing precision to impact prediction through the proposed model, the article seeks to ensure that the implementation evolves in sync with the specification, attacking the direct cause of RTD Type 2.</p>	
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S24	Type 0: Incomplete Stakeholder Needs	<p>The article evaluates the use of ChatGPT to extract information from app reviews and app descriptions. Mining these "general" artifacts is a fundamental technique in RE to identify user concerns, new features, and bugs that may not have been initially captured, ensuring that the needs of these stakeholders are not neglected.</p>	<p>The article investigates the potential and limitations of large language models in supporting Requirements Engineering processes through data extraction and text classification.</p> <p>The study conducts an empirical evaluation of ChatGPT in a zero-shot scenario (meaning no prior training examples were provided at the time of the query). An evaluation framework was designed combining two tasks (Classification and Extraction) with two types of requirements artifacts: specialized (developer-oriented documents, such as specifications and user stories) and general (oriented toward both developers and users, such as app descriptions and reviews).</p> <p>ChatGPT was tested via API across four benchmark datasets, using manual prompts to extract domain terms, identify functionalities, and classify Non-Functional Requirements (NFRs). Performance was measured quantitatively (using metrics such as precision, recall, and F-measure) in comparison to other established methodologies, followed by a qualitative analysis of the responses.</p> <p>The article focuses heavily on the mining of end-user artifacts, such as app reviews and ratings in virtual stores. Analyzing this content helps recover user feedback, bug reports, and feature requests that may not have been elicited by business analysts during the initial phases, aligning with RTD Type 0.</p>	LLM
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S25	Type 1: Requirement Smells	<p>The article proposes the use of Large Language Models (LLMs) and NLP to remove noise, automating the formalization of textual requirements prone to ambiguities and smells. By transforming them into structured models, the approach facilitates the detection of these issues and the verification of completeness.</p>	<p>The article addresses the challenge and the error-prone effort of extracting formal domain models from natural language requirements. Specifically, the study focuses on requirements expressed as user stories within agile product backlogs.</p> <p>The problem was investigated by comparing automated Artificial Intelligence and NLP techniques to extract structured concepts directly from raw text.</p> <p>Three distinct extraction approaches were compared:</p> <p>State-of-the-practice tool: A tool used for conceptual model extraction.</p> <p>LLM: Specifically GPT-3.5, interacting conversationally through prompt engineering and function calls restricted to JSON schemas.</p> <p>Dedicated NLP approach: A supervised method based on Conditional Random Fields (CRF), which analyzes the context and the semantic role of words within user stories.</p> <p>By utilizing these approaches, the authors seek to remove noise and increase the signal present in requirements texts.</p> <p>The article tackles the vulnerability inherent in free text: by automatically transforming potentially ambiguous user stories into structured models, it provides a formalization tool that mitigates the propagation of RTD Type 1.</p>	LLM
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S26	Type 1: Requirement Smells	<p>The objective of the article is to compare tools (rule-based vs. ChatGPT) for ambiguity detection in requirements documents. An analysis of requirements expressed in natural language was conducted to identify natural language defects. The tested tools (such as QuARS) perform lexical and syntactic analysis to pinpoint defective requirements.</p>	<p>The article addresses the phenomenon of ambiguity in software requirements documents that are expressed informally through natural language sentences.</p> <p>The study treats this phenomenon through a comparative analysis between two technological approaches for ambiguity detection: a traditional rule-based NLP tool (called QuARS) and a LLM based on Artificial Intelligence (ChatGPT).</p> <p>The authors perform the following process:</p> <p>They utilize four sample requirements documents (Coffee machine, E-shop, Library, DigitalHome).</p> <p>The requirements were submitted to both tools to extract potential linguistic defects, based on known ambiguity classes such as homonymy, vagueness, anaphoric pronouns, passive voice, and quantifier issues.</p> <p>They manually review the results to classify true positives (actual ambiguities) and false alarms.</p> <p>Finally, they evaluate and compare the tools' performance using quantitative metrics of precision and recall.</p> <p>RTD Type 1 refers to the problems and debt acquired exactly at the moment when user requirements are formalized into a specification document, especially when using natural language.</p> <p>In the study, the tools are used to analyze plain-text requirements documents and point out typical language defects, corresponding to RTD Type 1.</p>	LLM
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S27	Type 0: Incomplete Stakeholder Needs	<p>The article discusses the notion of external completeness, which refers to ensuring that requirements cover all information suggested by external sources. The proposed methodology simulates incompleteness by masking parts of a specification to verify if the model (BERT) can predict the missing terminology. It focuses on discovering what has not been written.</p>	<p>The article addresses incompleteness in system and software requirements written in natural language. It focuses on the challenge of improving and verifying external completeness, which is the concept of ensuring that the requirements document covers all information and knowledge suggested by external sources, such as the stakeholders themselves.</p> <p>The study proposes an approach that employs LLMs, particularly BERT, as an automated source of external knowledge to identify potential omissions in requirements. The approach simulates missing information by hiding parts of the requirements document. It utilizes BERT's Masked Language Modeling (MLM) functionality, masking nouns or verbs in the visible requirements so that the model generates contextualized predictions of terms that could fill those gaps.</p> <p>The solution seeks to identify relevant terminology and concepts missing from the document, using the BERT database to act as a virtual stakeholder or knowledge source. This source points out valuable information that the requirements analyst failed to collect and document initially, aligning with the mitigation of RTD Type 0.</p>	Approach
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S28	<p>Type 1: Requirement Smells and Type 2: Incompatible Implementation</p>	<p>The article discusses a tool that forces the user to adhere to a specific grammar (fields such as scope, condition, component, shall, timing, and response). This eliminates vague and subjective constructions (smells), ensuring that the requirement meets semantic quality standards that allow for logical formalization. The tool generates verification code that can be utilized by analysis tools to verify whether the model or implemented code satisfies the specified requirements.</p>	<p>The phenomenon addressed in the article is ambiguity in the elicitation and documentation of requirements in natural language, which hinders formal analysis in safety-critical systems. Furthermore, the article tackles the challenge of ensuring and verifying that the software implementation (whether in code or models) accurately corresponds to these high-level requirements stipulated at the project's outset.</p> <p>The article treats this phenomenon by presenting the FRET (Formal Requirements Elicitation Tool).</p> <p>The tool requires users to write requirements using a restricted and intuitive natural language called FRETish, which possesses a precise and unambiguous semantic meaning. To assist analysts, FRET automatically produces text-based and diagrammatic explanations, in addition to offering an interactive visualizer to simulate temporal relationships, ensuring that the formalized requirement reflects the author's true intent. To validate the implementation, the tool mathematically formalizes the requirements (using temporal logic) and allows for the mapping of abstract requirements variables to the actual signals and variables contained in the software models or the implementation source code.</p> <p>By utilizing the FRETish language and providing dynamic grammar and diagrams during editing, the tool eliminates the ambiguities and imprecisions typical of conventional specification documents, relating to Type 1 RTD. The article also addresses combating the mismatch between specification and implementation through its requirements analysis</p>	Tool
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			module, relating to the mitigation of RTD Type 2.	
S29	Type 1: Requirement Smells and Type 2: Incompatible Implementation	The objective of the study is to transform natural language into formal rules (using ontologies and the SWRL rule language) to avoid natural language ambiguity and make requirements clear, explicit, and concise. Furthermore, it seeks to bridge the gap between system requirements and design models, focusing on verifying whether the designed models meet the system requirements.	<p>The article addresses the ambiguity and abstraction inherent in requirements expressed in natural language during the specification phase.</p> <p>To solve this problem, a requirements formalization method is proposed. Instead of maintaining requirements in free text, the approach utilizes templates (structured models) to transform natural language requirements into precise formal rules for logical reasoning (using the SWRL language).</p> <p>By transforming natural language into computable and rigorous logical rules, the article removes ambiguities, ensuring that the specification becomes clear, explicit, and concise before moving to the next project phase, relating to the mitigation of RTD Type 1 and 2.</p>	Approach

S30	Type 1: Requirement Smells	<p>The objective of the article is to identify and clarify ambiguous terms in the requirements specification, such as vague adverbs and adjectives (e.g., "fast," "relatively," "high quality"). It utilizes the natural language criteria from the ISO/IEC/IEEE 29148 standard to compile a list of ambiguous terms to be detected.</p>	<p>The article addresses ambiguity in requirements specifications for large-scale projects, highlighting that product requirements are typically written in natural language, which is inherently imprecise and susceptible to multiple interpretations.</p> <p>The problem is handled through the proposal of a semi-automated approach called NLP-FUZZ. The approach utilizes Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques, specifically POS tagging (Part-Of-Speech tagging), to automatically scan the text and find potentially ambiguous terms. The ISO/IEEE/IEC 29148 standard is used to categorize which adverbs, adjectives, and comparative phrases should be flagged. To not only identify but also resolve the problem, the method applies Fuzzy Logic to the identified terms. The automated system extracts the problematic sentence and asks two simple questions to a Subject Matter Expert (SME) to establish mathematical parameters (thresholds in fuzzy graphs) for what is acceptable for that term. This transforms vague words (large, recent) into clarified and verifiable metrics.</p> <p>The focus is on fixing vague requirements document text, aligning with the mitigation of Type 1 RTD.</p>	Approach
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S31	Type 1: Requirement Smells	The article emphasizes the issue of quality and the correct formulation of requirements. It mentions the use of LLMs to "address ambiguity" and ensure that the language does not violate quality standards.	<p>The article addresses biases and ambiguities in requirements formulation during Ontology Requirements Engineering (ORE), which results in the production of ill-formed requirements. This problem occurs primarily due to inefficient collaboration between knowledge engineers and domain experts, as well as the absence of real-time intelligent assistance during the requirements elicitation and documentation phase.</p> <p>The use of LLMs is proposed to act as virtual knowledge engineers. The study describes the development of an LLM-based system called OntoChat, which utilizes a user-centered methodology known as Participatory Prompting. The system guides domain experts through conversational flows and libraries of prompt templates, helping them iteratively structure and refine their needs. The primary objective is to ensure that the process outputs are well-formed requirements, evaluating them based on quality criteria such as consistency, completeness, correlation, and absence of ambiguities.</p> <p>The article focuses directly on mitigating formalization and drafting defects during the creation of the requirements specification, aligning with RTD Type 1.</p>	Approach
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S32	Type 0 (Incomplete Stakeholder Needs) e a Type 1 (Requirement Smells).	<p>The article presents ReqBrain, an artificial intelligence tool based on a fine-tuned language model for the automated generation of software requirements. The authors developed a specialized dataset following the ISO 29148 standard to train small-scale models, aiming to overcome slow and imprecise manual processes. Through rigorous evaluations, the Zephyr-7b-beta model stood out by producing authentic requirements that human experts could not distinguish from human-written texts. The system integrates the elicitation and specification phases, allowing engineers to interact via chat to identify knowledge gaps and organize technical demands. The results demonstrate that specialized fine-tuning allows smaller models to outperform generic systems like ChatGPT-4o in specific engineering tasks.</p>	<p>The article addresses the manual, labor-intensive, and error-prone process of requirements elicitation and specification.</p> <p>To solve this problem, ReqBrain is introduced an AI-assisted tool that utilizes a fine-tuned LLM to automate and enhance requirements generation. The tool tackles the problem through specific training tasks:</p> <p>To address information omission: The model features the "Missing INST" capability, which simulates scenarios where the requirements set is incomplete and challenges the AI to identify and generate the missing requirements.</p> <p>To address writing ambiguity: The model uses the "How-to? INST" capability, which forces the AI to generate requirements by strictly following the syntaxes and signaling keywords recommended by the ISO 29148 standard.</p> <p>The tool merges the elicitation and specification phases, allowing for the generation of clear and actionable requirements to occur in real-time while gathering needs, thereby reducing rework.</p> <p>The tool suggests missing requirements (increasing the overall completeness of the document) and encourages the engineer to ask the right questions to extract needs that the stakeholder did not initially verbalize, aligning with the mitigation of RTD Type 0.</p> <p>The article points out that the lack of structured syntax in natural language leads to vague and ambiguous requirements. This is the very definition of a Requirement Smell. ReqBrain eliminates this debt at the source by not allowing the requirement to be formalized in a free-form manner. It converts raw intentions into</p>	Tool
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			well-formed requirements, applying high-quality standards from ISO 29148 (such as the [Subject][Action][Constraint] templates), ensuring that the SRS is born free of language ambiguities and imprecisions.	
S33	Type 0 (Incomplete Stakeholder Needs) e a Type 1 (Requirement Smells).	The article evaluates the quality of functional specifications generated by LLMs (GPT, Gemini, Claude, DeepSeek) for a management system. It measures completeness by comparing the AI-generated artifacts with a human-written reference specification, calculating Precision, Recall, and F1 Score. Furthermore, it assesses whether the statements are accurate, grammatically correct, and free from multiple interpretations.	<p>The article investigates the capability and effectiveness of LLMs in automating the generation of functional requirements specifications for software development. Specifically, the study analyzes how four popular models (GPT, Claude, Gemini, and DeepSeek) succeed in extracting and structuring requirements artifacts Use Cases, Business Rules, and Collaborative Workflows.</p> <p>A zero-shot prompting technique was used to request the four LLMs to generate requirements artifacts from the system's problem statement. The AI-generated artifacts were compared against a detailed reference specification previously created by humans following Agile methodologies. The quality of the generated requirements was rigorously evaluated through four criteria: Syntactic and Semantic Correctness, Consistency, Unambiguity, and Completeness. To avoid bias, the evaluations were conducted in a blind review process, where the evaluators did not know which LLM had generated which requirement when assigning scores. Completeness was measured mathematically using Precision, Recall, and F1 Score formulas.</p> <p>By addressing the Completeness criterion, the study directly tackles RTD Type 0. The article also investigates RTD Type 1 through the applied criteria of Syntactic and Semantic Correctness, Consistency, and Unambiguity.</p>	Approach

S34	Type 2: Incompatible Implementation	<p>The article investigates the use of LLMs to verify whether a system technical specification (which describes the technical solution, workflows, and system interactions) fulfills a given set of requirements.</p>	<p>The article addresses requirements verification, specifically focusing on evaluating whether a system's technical specification complies with a set of pre-established requirements.</p> <p>An experimental study is conducted to compare the performance of LLMs against traditional rule-based expert systems. The LLMs (such as GPT-4o, Claude 3.5 Sonnet, Gemini 1.5, and GPT-3.5-turbo) are provided with textual descriptions of system specifications along with a set of requirements written in natural language. The models receive instructions (via prompts) to analyze the text and identify which requirements are fulfilled, which are not fulfilled, and which do not apply to that specific specification. The quality of the verification is measured using metrics (precision, recall, and F1-score) and analyzes how different variables affect the results, such as: the complexity of the system specification, the number of requirements provided, the clarity of the textual style, and the use of different prompting strategies.</p> <p>The article aims to detect and alert regarding the mismatch between the established goals (requirements) and the solution's implementation, aligning with the mitigation of RTD Type 2.</p>	LLM
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S35	Type 1: Requirement Smells	<p>The methodology proposed in the article utilizes LLMs and Knowledge Graphs to transform unstructured, prolix, and complex text into structured and standardized data. The article introduces information extraction templates based on the SysML (System Modeling Language) standard to categorize requirements into five types: functional, interface, performance, physical, and design constraints.</p>	<p>The article addresses the ambiguity, imprecision, and lack of structure inherent in requirements documents written in natural language. It is highlighted that traditional manual document-based management leads to interpretational inconsistencies, poor information interrelation, and high management complexity, hindering traceability and the understanding of dependencies between requirements in complex systems.</p> <p>An integrated prompt-guided framework is proposed, combining LLMs, specifically GPT-4 and Knowledge Graphs (KGs).</p> <p>The unstructured text is classified into five requirements categories defined by the SysML language (functional, interface, performance, physical, and design constraints).</p> <p>Information extraction templates were created to guide the LLM in dissecting verbose natural language sentences, isolating crucial and structured elements such as the subject, object, action, and conditions.</p> <p>After converting the free text into structured data, the system automatically constructs a Knowledge Graph, which visually illustrates the interdependencies, hierarchies, and semantic constraints among the system requirements.</p> <p>The focus of the article is the correction of problems originating during the formalization of requirements in natural language, aligning with the mitigation of RTD Type 1.</p>	LLM
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S36	Type 0 (Incomplete Stakeholder Needs)	The article discusses the utilization of the NLP4ReF tool, which was used to generate requirements that were "previously missing," filling the gaps left during the analysis phase.	<p>The article addresses the phenomenon of incompleteness and volatility of requirements in software and systems projects, specifically the problem of hidden, forgotten, missing, and constantly evolving requirements. The authors highlight that traditional Requirements Engineering methods face significant difficulties in capturing all needs, which frequently results in failures. The text illustrates this phenomenon by analyzing a real-life Internet of Things (IoT) project that failed precisely due to an "inadequate understanding of customer needs."</p> <p>To resolve the issue of missing or incomplete requirements, the article introduces the NLP4ReF (Natural Language Processing for Requirement Forecasting) methodology.</p> <p>The method treats the phenomenon through an approach based on generative artificial intelligence and Machine Learning models (utilizing NLTK and the ChatGPT API). The tool operates in two main ways:</p> <p>Organization and Classification: It organizes the initial requirements, separating them into functional/non-functional categories and by system classes.</p> <p>Requirements Forecasting: This is the core capability to autonomously generate new, unforeseen, hidden, or forgotten requirements based on an initial set.</p>	Ferramenta
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			The tool seeks to automatically generate and predict essential requirements that were "forgotten" or neglected during the initial communication phase with the client, corresponding to RTD Type 0.	
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